

IDENTITY AND NATIONHOOD: PSYCHOLOGICAL PERSPECTIVES ON MUSLIM NATIONALISM IN SOUTH ASIA

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ABSTRACT

This research deals with the psychological factors which played a crucial role in strengthening Muslim Nationalism in Sub-continent. After coming under British rule, economic disparities, lack of political representation, fear of losing religious and cultural identity, cognitive profiles of educated broad minded Muslim leaders like Sir Syed Ahmad Khan and observational patterns of global change like end of Ottoman Empire and Russian revolution had great impact on Muslims. They tried to eradicate negative sentiments from their hearts to rebuild their selves in order to regain their lost identity back beneath the flag of Muslim nationalism. This research seeks how historical and socio-cultural circumstances formulated the psychological basis of Muslim Nationalism in Sub-continent. The research is currently significant as the knowledge about the psychological dynamics of any social movement or concept helps in determining the complex human behavior behind any big historical change. It assists in determining the reasons behind power-shift in any society and can also help in correlating past events with the present, in order to predict future for the convenience of policy makers. This study is equally beneficial for researchers of social sciences, psychology as well as historians and political scientists.

INTRODUCTION

Muslim nationalism is a relatively new phenomenon, arose predominantly in the 19th century in the sub-continent. The British imperialism was the chief propagating factor behind it and like all other pronounced changes, it produced all around the globe at that time. It is justified if the credit of emergence of Muslim nationalism is given to British imperialistic approach. It cannot be labelled as a conventional idea, because it ensued a great geographical change in the region. Hindus and Muslims who were living together for more than a millennium, parted their ways on permanent grounds. Other than many factors that functioned as a promoter of this idea, there is a complex psychological phenomenon behind the multi-layered concept of Muslim nationalism. An intricate pattern of human

behavior worked behind the transition of the traditional layout of Muslim society in the sub-continent. The ill treatment and the injustice of the British towards Muslims, and the fear of losing their cultural heritage, fueled Muslims to adopt a new pattern of identity. The new pattern on later stage transformed into Muslim nationalism gradually.

The aftermaths of War of independence were vilest for Indian especially for those who were the believers of Islam. As the riots of Indians in 1857 were frustrating for the English invaders, so after controlling the rebellion, they were not ready to spare the responsible. Muslims were the major targets because they were suspected as master-minds behind the mutiny. Muslims had to face torment, which British levied on them. That

situation was really hard on their souls and they were emotionally affected. Moreover, when the sub-continent became British India, Muslims were not given their due share. Their economic condition was very fragile and politically, they were not having any sort of representation on any prominent position. Their cultural and religious identities were also on stake. It developed frustration and pessimism among them but soon, undesirable sentiments of shame and deprivation in Muslims triggered due to their exploitation by the hands of British and Hindus. That situation gradually had been converted into a source of motivation to start struggle for their survival as a separate entity, under the defense mechanism of their minds. The guidance of sincere leadership as well as socio-cultural, economical and historical factors revised the thought-process of Muslims of India and they steadily become more concerned about their rights and future. This consciousness of Muslims, fostered the emotions of pride and self-determination in them, which ultimately proved as a substructure for Muslim Nationalism; a ray of hope for a community who had suffered a collective trauma after being thrown from the crown of sub-continent.

This research employs interdisciplinary approach connecting a social phenomenon with human psychology and would be based on primary as well as secondary data in the form of credible books from prime witnesses, research articles, newspapers sources as well as interview from a notable psychologist in order to get clarity about the topic under research

Theoretical Framework

This study carries theoretical frame work and several theories can explain the psychological roots of Muslims nationalism like social identity theory, relative deprivation theory and acculturation theory of sociology. Social Identity theory predicts those circumstances under which an individual identifies himself and other members of a society as a separate group on the basis of some specific characters. It is also linked with a cataloging of individuals to distinguish their in- group with the other groups on the basis of some positive attributes.(Sohail, D, Personal Communication, January 13th, 2024).In this way, we can relate our research with Social Identity theory as Muslims of

Sub-continent categorized themselves as a separate entity on the basis of their religion i.e. Islam and they believed to have many positive attributes adopted from the teaching of Islam. It developed sense of pride among them being Muslims and made them unique as separate group within the diverse society of their country. These sentiments further advanced collective sense of identity in Muslims, which laid the base of Muslim Nationalism.

Similarly, relative deprivation theory of psychology by Ted Gurr is also linked with this research. It states that injustice, cruelty and depriving people from their basic rights nurture distress and inferiority complex in them as a group as compared to the others who are in much better condition. This theory also suggests that such type of feeling often instill unity among those who are under bad circumstances, which sets groundwork for great social movements in order to resolve all those issues. (Gordon,2019).Psychological base of Muslim Nationalism can be linked with relative deprivation theory as the oppression and injustice by British, disheartened Muslims and they started feeling less privileged as compared to Hindus and other communities .This negative sentiment diverted the minds of Muslims to gather courage and start their efforts for the sake of their survival. Acculturation theory of sociology deals with the phenomenon that when people from one culture come in first hand, continuous and prolonged contact with the individuals with totally different culture, it initiates a process of cultural change. This change occurs, both at individual and group level. (Redfield et.al, 1936). This theory articulates the framework through which specific segment of society adopts new cultural norms and patterns of behavior.¹The link of acculturation theory to Muslim nationalism can be seen when British invaded Sub-continent, their culture was entirely different from the local inhabitants. Their way of living, political and religious norms were not similar to Muslims and other communities who were inhabitants of Sub-continent. Muslims adopted few things from British culture e.g. language and education but at the same time, tried to preserve their distinct individuality. We can study in history that leaders like Sir Syed tried really hard to bring closeness among Muslims and British. At the same time, they tried to avoid

assimilation in Muslim cultural characteristics and dominant British cultural heritage, to maintain their distinctiveness, which was the primary factor behind the Muslim nationalist movement.

Muslim Nationalism: True Meanings

Muslim nationalism began its evolutionary journey since the early years of the nineteenth century but it took its final track in the first half of 20th century, when great modifications happened in the socio-cultural strata of the sub-continent which redesigned the landscape of the region. Power shift in the sub-continent after decline of Mughal rule, sense of deprivation and intolerant behavior of the new rulers, laid great impacts on psychology of Muslims. But it did not instigate much damage because marvelous leadership of Sir Syed Ahmad Khan and other prominent Muslim influential, converted the negativity, instilled in their minds into a motivation to be out of that situation. (Ahmad & Haider, 2024). This enthusiasm, promulgated nationalism in Muslims, which further grabbed many forms and unfolded a much better compensation of all the grievance faced by Muslims, i.e. a separate state for them in the North West of the sub-continent.

Before discussing Muslim Nationalism and its psychological genesis in detail, it is important to explore that what nationalism actually means. Nationalism is feeling of oneness among people of a certain group on the basis of some particular character e.g. common language, culture, race or religion. Christopher R Fardan and Catherine Thorleifsson define Nationalism as an ideology which holds the concept that state and the nation should be united and nationalist groups exclude themselves on cultural, racial and ethnic grounds. (Fardan & Thorleifsson, 2020). In *Al Majmo Wasit* published in Cairo in 1999, nationalism has been described as a relation of people formed within society on the basis of cohesion of interests and also common gender and language and it promotes mutual cooperation. (Mustafa, Alzayat, Abdul Qadir & Alnajar, 1999). So by keeping in view the above explanation of the concept of nationalism, Muslim Nationalism in sub-continent can be defined as feeling developed in the minds of Muslim leaders that they were dissimilar from the other communities living in the same geographical region especially Hindus and have variances into many aspects of life like social and cultural life. This sentiment of congruence among Muslim

leaders was transferred into masses and it grew stronger and stronger owing to different events at the advent of twentieth century, Muslim nationalism dynamically braced Muslims to reform themselves politically and be a part of all political activities in the region under British rule, which was very necessary to maintain their sole identity. So it is clear that firm sense of Muslim Nationalism was the protective shield for Muslims in the crucial first half of the century, and they were able to get Pakistan, after the British left the sub-continent just because of the fact that they were already politically advanced. If Muslims were not together under the umbrella of Muslim Nationalism, then they might come under Hindu majority rule after British's departure because a democratic government always support majority. By keeping in view the above details, the accurate definition of Muslim Nationalism in words of Sharif Al Mujahid is as follow:

Muslim nationalism is a central way between pan-Islamism and pure nationalism. A blend of these two opposing ideologies i.e. Muslim nationalism, endeavors to promote the solidarity, and close collaboration between the numerous Muslim sections on the basis of their religious like-mindedness and cultural unity. (Mujahid, 1999).

Psychological factors leading Muslims towards Muslim Nationalism:

Muslim nationalism was basically an emotional reaction of Muslims, under specific unpleasant circumstances. With the loss of the rule and after failure of the War of Independence 1857, Muslims were majorly blamed for the so called 'rebellion.' Muslims dwelled into a very dark phase of disparity and frustration, where they were totally clueless about their future. They were dispersed, immobilized and lacked any form of leadership after the exile of last Mughal Emperor Bahadur Shah Zafar and the execution of his sons. As they were charged of prompting the uprising in 1857, British tried to deprive them of all kind of facilities. Then, they were utterly crumbling especially in economic and political domains. Human mind has unique ability to develop different kind of defense mechanisms under unpleasant, painful and unavoidable agonizing situations, which either cause numbness in humans to compromise and accept the situation, or sometimes converts negative emotions into a positive motivation, to adopt non-compromising policy and instill

courage. That new courage witnesses struggle for the improvement of their bereaved condition. (Glinka, 2013) This human instinct was clearly depicted in the response of Muslims who were facing barbaric revenge of British, when they refused to accept their miseries as their final fate, gathered their hopes and got motivated to mend their condition and that constructive response commanded them to be together under Muslim Nationalism. Following are the psychological factors which provided base to the Muslim nationalism:

Identity Crisis:

Muslims emerged as a strong political and cultural reality in Sub-continent with the inception of Slave Dynasty in India, which was the beginning of a long centuries old glorified era of Muslim rule. Since that time, Muslims had an unvarying part in power. It helped them to grow their culture and deepen their identity in the Sub-continent which was a hub of different ethnicities and religions. Muslim rulers, who were not inhabitants, built a multifaceted Islamic civilization in this area, the mixture of Turk, Afghani, Arab and Persian cultures, which gave a divergent and unique value to Islamic culture in Sub-continent. (Language: Urdu and the borrowed words, 2011). It is not a misperception if someone says that Muslims lacks unity and cultural bonding during the earlier years of Muslim rule but Muslim monarchs especially those who belonged to Delhi and Mughal dynasties cultivated the cultural heritage of Islam, which was not directly linked to Indian culture but a blend of divergent elements because Muslims of sub continents were mostly divided into two categories, the one who invaded sub-continent and were foreigners and the second group was of indigenous settlers mostly consisting of low class Hindus and Sikhs as well as indigenous Muslims. (Kiran, 2008). The locals continued to practice their traditional Indian living style. This synthesis of indigenous cultural values was clearly depicted in the arts, architecture and also in language. Urdu language became the prime symbol of Muslim identity being a fusion of Arabic, Turkish, Persian and many other local dialects. (Hamid, 2021) Urdu grew as lingua franca, a language which served as a bridge between people belonging to different racial and religious backgrounds. The work of renowned poets and writers built a thick literary legacy, portraying as Muslim cultural identity in sub-

continent. Though Muslim community was not integrated and divided into different sections, still Urdu became the source of shared unity and code of individuality among them. Spiritual festivals, religious rituals and practices fetched Muslims together including the *Muharram*, *Milaaad* and *Eid* gatherings and processions by different sects of Muslims. It strengthened the collective identity of Muslims and they had developed great and splendid cultural heritage in pre-colonial era. (Mujahid, 1999)

Urdu achieved a distinct status in 1850's when Mughal emperor Bahadur Shah Zafar used it as a medium to express his sentiments through poems. Lithography was also introduced in Sub-continent around late 1830s through which Urdu newspapers and magazines started showing their impact as compared to the reading material of other languages. Urdu became the symbol of Muslim identity and the source of communication for both Indian elites and Muslim masses. (Hamid, 2021). Hindus started Urdu-Hindi controversy in Banaras in 1867 and tried to replace Urdu by Hindi. It prompted Muslims and they found it quite offensive and threat to their cultural identity. From this point onwards, Muslims started developing a new mind and became insecure about their religious and cultural identity in India under British, strongly dominated by Hindus who were putting a constant pressure to replace Urdu by Hindi on official level. Muslims became more determined and strong to save their character when in 1898 Urdu was replaced by Hindi in the Northern Western Province's lower courts. After this, Muslims were too sure that if they did not respond collectively against all such efforts to vanish them ideologically, they would not be able to save their individual character as a separate group.

British priests also tried to attract the population of Sub-continent towards Christianity. They started sending missionaries to every important place like schools, hospitals, prisons and even they started preaching in the markets. (Sen, 1989). Muslims, throughout their ruling period, were never upset of living in a multi-religious society. Religion became a point of concern for them after coming under British rule. Hindu extremism and growing role of Christian missionaries alarmed them to preserve their religious identity. So in this way, identity crisis propagated the seeds of Muslim

nationalism as their historical roots and cultural identity was in a threat.

Political Rights

Muslims of India were not politically developed and lagging behind Hindus due to the language barrier. Majority of Muslims were unaware of English language and unable to get significant representation in administration, decision making process and other higher level jobs. British, too, intentionally kept them away from such responsible designations. They were favoring Hindus as they had readily accepted the new masters. Hindus were already under rule of Muslims, so the change in the power dynamics did not impact them much. That situation was quite frustrating for Muslims as they were the ruling elites of the region for centuries and were not comfortable with their new less-privileged status. Muslims were not fairly treated and getting their due share in government and other influencing posts. (Khan, 1873) While explaining the same phenomenon, Sir Syed Ahmad Khan, in his short book *Causes of Indian Revolt* wrote:

The whole Indian society was suppressed due to bad administration of the British government and it was the dissatisfaction of whole nation, not only Muslims which evolved into an armed resistance against the rulers. Lack of representation in political institutions like legislative assemblies, and efforts to force Muslims to convert into Christianity developed the sense of insecurity and pushed the Muslim masses into a phase where they started believing that they lost their identity after end of Mughal era. (Khan 1873)

Even to become a voter of executive and provincial legislature, Muslims had to pay tax on income of three thousand a year. Resultantly, Muslims voters were very less even in Muslim majority provinces. (Hamid, 2018) Muslims were in that state of mind where they were well aware of the fact that they were relatively deprived of many of the civil rights and liberties in comparison to Hindus. But fortunately, Muslims had smooth leadership, who energetically started directing their people in the accurate way. They influenced Muslims by inculcating positivity in their minds for the British. Sir Syed advised Muslims to focus more on developing their selves instead of demanding for political representation in the beginning, so that they would be able to participate in future constitutional reforms. (Mondal, 2017). This

mentality and approach helped Muslims to seek education and got trust of the British. They strengthened them politically by making their own political party i.e. All India Muslim League in 1906, which secured a right of separate electorates for them in Minto-Morley reforms of 1909. (Tripathi, 2014). It gave a big boost to the concept of Muslim Nationalism. The disparity caused in Muslims due to political deprivation, became a source of developing solid Muslim nationalism.

Economic Disparities

Muslims of India faced severe economic challenges after losing their power. Their socio-economic condition became worst after war of Independence. There were numerous reason behind new economic challenges. British imposed heavy taxes on land owners. British land revenue policies were quite tough on Muslim peasant's. Hefty amount of land revenues were collected from Muslim land owners which negatively affected their financial condition. (Hamid 2018). William Hunter portrayed the condition of Muslims in these words:

It was nearly impossible for Muslims who were born in rich families, to become poor ever in their lives, but after mutiny it is now impossible for any Muslim to become rich ever. (Hunter, 1871).

The unequal distribution of wealth and unfair distribution of jobs pushed the Muslims in backward situation. They were deprived of all important and honorable jobs, and other communities were given priority over them. Industries and technical facilities were in non-Muslim majority areas, so Muslims struggled really hard to get reasonable jobs for their survival. In all government offices, Muslims were only given jobs of messenger, peons, porters and peons. Financial crisis and failure to give good lives to their families instigated Muslims to be concerned about their future and they became truly mindful to be active enough to fight against the odds. (Hunter, 1871). Was living and surrendering to those circumstances, a wise thing? Absolutely not. Muslims were conscious to converse their monetary state. They desired for better living conditions. Their yearning to improve their economic condition, gave them strength and courage, which ultimately played its part in propagating the passion of reviving their old grandeur and glory. (New York Daily Tribune,

1858). It, finally, converted into a movement which later was called as Muslim nationalist movement.

Harsh Behavior

Immediately after crushing the war of independence, British prompted a horrible revenge against the responsible people. As they perceived Muslims as the main culprits, so they became the victim of worst rage of British Army. They were extremely furious and implemented severe punishments for Muslims. That was the darkest period for them. All the sympathizers of the rebellion were executed and mass trials of hundreds of suspected Muslims especially in Delhi was conducted. Muslims faced brutal reprisals, executions, violence and displacement. The British even blamed, without finding any evidence, that armed Indians had abused and molested English women during the rebellion, only to justify their barbaric activities in front of their public in United Kingdom. (Kaye, 1910). They passed Act. No. XIV of 1857, even before suppressing the rebellion, to legalize retributions against the rebels. The Act said that any person who was found guilty of taking part in the rebellion, would be sentenced to death, and their facilitator would also be liable to heavy penalties. (Government of India, 1857). Under the shadow of this Act, they took all the brutal steps against Muslims after fall of Delhi. Almost 1400 unarmed people were slaughtered, in neighborhood of Delhi, Kacha Chalan. John William Kaye writes, about Delhi massacre "Various people who had never struck a blow against us, were stabbed by our knives, or killed by our rifles. In the first few days of our occupation of Delhi, many innocent men were shot down or otherwise exterminated." (Ahmad & Aijaz, 2023). The events after the end of War of Independence, deeply affected Muslims and they were drenched in fear and hopelessness but they were not mentally defeated. The immoral oppression of British had a profound impact on Muslims and they felt severe humiliation. They responded positively to their new leadership, who encouraged them to start striving for their betterment future in place of crying on their wounds of past. It was also another psychological factor which led them towards Muslim nationalism.

Observational Elements

Observation of local and global events always has an impact on the decisions and policies of "if not all" but at least those who are directly or in directly connected to those events. Since the inception of 20th century, Muslim nationalism was flourished quickly because of many global events which laid deep impacts on the minds of Muslims. World War I, in which Britain was direct participant and was in opposing group of the great Ottoman Empire, had significant impacts on all around the world especially on British colonies. Shifts in power dynamics especially fear to lose the Caliphate in Ottoman Empire distressed Muslims of South Asia and they became more mindful about their survival. It fortified the concept of Pan Islamism in Sub-continent against the colonial powers. Muslim Nationalism observed a new character after the end of WWI, when a number of Muslims started promoting Pan Islamism that means Muslims are one beyond geographical boundaries. Though local *Muftis* and *Ulema* were issuing *fatawas* in favor of *Jihad* since the beginning of WWI but when allies of Ottoman empire lost the war, Muslims of sub-continent launched a massive *Khilafat* movement., It was the reflection of strong sentimental connection of Muslims to the Ottoman empire, as they believed that it was the mark of Islamic strength and unity. (Khimji, 2013).

Khilafat movement was led by renowned Muslim leaders like Muhammad Ali Johar, Mualana Zafar Ali Khan, Mualana Shokat Ali and later acquired support from Hindu leaders like Gandhi, who also provoked Muslims to initiate Non Cooperation moment against the government. Though this movement failed to save the integrity of Ottoman Empire but it had a great impact to shape the politics of Muslims of India and made them politically more mature. The Muslims who were together under *Khilafat* Movement, conducted rallies, huge gatherings, faced detentions and arrests and even left Sub-continent under influence of Mulana Abdul Kalam Azad's *fatwa* of leaving *dar ul hub* (sub-continent). It prepared them for another movement i.e. Pakistan movement which was result of Muslim nationalism. Muslims, who were politically activated during *Khilafat* movement, were well mindful of the sacrifices and hard work which was required to fulfil their dream of separate homeland after passing of Lahore resolution. In this way, *Khilafat* movement also

helped to flourish Muslim nationalism. (Khimji, 2013).

Russian Revolution of 1917, which resulted in a strong communist Soviet Union also had deep impacts all around the world. Russian revolution ended Tsarist government and established new government who was following ideas of socialism. The revolution, also known as Bolshevik Revolution, was the change of Imperialistic Tsar government of Nicholas II into a Socialist government of Lenin. (Oxford references). The socialist revolutionaries were following the principle of Karl Marx, who gave the Idea of class less society, where no one was allowed to have private property, so that workers or labor class was not suppressed by the elite class.² The capitalist world was very critical of this change in Russia, and were feeling threatened that the ideology might spread in their own countries and colonies. (Afridi, 2022). It was the time when Muslims were engaged into Khilafat movement in Sub-continent. Non-cooperation movement along with *hijrat* movement was also initiated against British Imperialist government. The Russian revolution had set a great example of resistance against the oppressive rules, so it attracted Muslims leaders too. That revolution was basically a model to struggle for regime-change in order to get their rights, so it was not possible that it did not affect the consciousness of Muslims of India too. Sikandar Hayat Afridi claims in his article that Marxist theory who served as a manifesto for Russian revolutionaries is the only theory that support revolts, uprising and armed protests against the oppressive government, so non-cooperation movement, *hijrat* movement and protest against rowed acts were all under the indirect influence of overall growing communist environment during the years related to Russian revolution. (Afridi, 2022) The failures of the *Khilafat* movement against British strengthened Muslim's belief that they had to grow stronger as a "Muslim community" to contest for their civil and political rights. Even the Edward Montagu's appointment, who remained the viceroy of Sub-continent during 1916 to 1921, was not appreciated by Anglo Indian community and he was called "British Bolshevik", when he was about to leave England. (Hamid, n.d) Basically Muslim Nationalism was the result of Muslim consciousness about their religion and identity. All

events which caused social awareness among Muslims were directly or in directly became the base of Muslim nationalism.

Cognitive Profiles of the Leaders

Cognitive profile of leaders matters a lot in shaping the future of that particular nation. Cognitive Profile means the relative weaknesses and strengths of individual which shape their personality. Cognitive behavior of Muslim leaders played a very crucial role in mounting positive attitude in Muslims. There were three main stream leaders who advanced the concept of nationalism among Muslims. Along with lots of other Muslim leaders who gave inspiration to Muslims to change their intention of living by striving for their rights, Sir Syed, Allama Iqbal and Muhammad Ali Jinnah were the real architects behind the concept of Muslim nationalism. These leaders had analytical and positive approach because they were highly educated and were not restricted to traditional thought process. Sir Syed Ahmad Khan was on high official post in British India and was well aware of British mentality. He witnessed a very important era in which descendants of Taimur had to leave their century's old rule and Muslims had to face the transition from being the elites to the sub ordinates of the people who were outsiders' (Sherwani, 1944). His judicious response to the war of Independence and its aftermaths shows his rational approach. He intuited that without getting the support of British, Muslims could not be able to revive their old status.

The optimistic and constructive approach of Sir Syed later, was seen in Muslim response to their bad circumstances. According to Sir Syed, religion was very important for progress so he considered principles of Islam conducive in the path of enlightenment. (Malik, 1968) Instead of compromising with their condition, Muslims who were under influence of Sir Syed started getting united with the feeling that they were a separate entity, and deserved all rights equal to British and Hindus. He launched Aligarh movement, which not only spread awareness among Muslims about their obligations and rights, but also reduced differences between Muslims and British. M.A.O College was formed by him, which later, up-graded to Aligarh University after the death of Sir Syed. This institution played a crucial role and gave a

logical echo to the voice of Muslims. (Malik, 1962). It did not support extremist views, had moderate ideology and the students of that university were the staunch advocates of Pakistan movement.

Jinnah and Iqbal were foreign qualified lawyers who spent many years in liberal environment of Europe. They had deep analytical approach to predict future of their nation and they guided Muslims according to their broad vision. These leaders initially had pro Indian approach but then due to uncomfortable circumstances for Muslims in sub-continent, the change in thought process of these leaders, owing to the evolution in cultural, political and religious factors of sub-continent, diverted the attention of Muslims towards the perseverance of their exclusive identity. The role of Sir Syed Ahmad Khan, Allama Iqbal and Quaid e Azam in developing nationalism among Muslims, was their spontaneous reaction to their environment. Even Sir Syed was not aware of the fact that the impact of his teachings and actions as a Muslim activist would reshape the track of Muslims towards a separate homeland. Iqbal's poetry mostly illustrates his philosophical ideas instead of his core political values. His poetry revolves around the concept of "Self", which encouraged Muslims not to compromise on their self-respect. The following verses clearly depict the idea. (Iqbal, 1932).

Diyar e Ishq main apa maqam paida kr
 Naya Zamana, Naye Subah o Sham paida kr
 (Build in love's empire your health and your home;
 Build Time a new, a new dawn, a new eve!

He encouraged Muslims to realize their inner potentials. This self-awareness helped them to understand their worth and they decided to stand against the injustices imposed upon them by the government. The concept, which is considered the core of Iqbal's poetry, somehow stimulate Muslims, left imprints on their psychology and they stood against the oppressors being one nation to get their due rights. Iqbal also evaluated weaknesses of Muslims, demonstrated through his writings and poetry that Muslims of sub-continent must developed attributes like determination, courage and simplicity in them, so that they plead more power as a distinct group being followers of Islam. (Ravi & Mishra, 2023). Iqbal's progressive leadership and his influential poetry had a profound impact on Muslim psyche, which ultimately took a path towards Muslim Nationalism. He also gave a hint of a separate state

for Muslim in his famous speech of All'abad, during Annual session of Muslim League in 1930. He also suggested in a letter to Quaid e Azam, to strive for a separate Muslim state just few months before his death. (Ashraf, 1943) so basically Allama Iqbal was one among many whose teachings inclined Muslims of India towards nationalist approach in the first half of the twentieth century.

Muhammad Ali Jinnah, who was given the title of Quaid-e-Azam, had charismatic personality with qualities like honesty, enthusiasm, optimism, straightforwardness with the ability to convince and inspire public. His cognitive profile was helpful in mesmerizing Muslims as his personality was the mixture of British liberalism which inspired him during his stay in England from 1902 to 1906. The "second" factor was multi cultured and commercial environment of Bombay, where he practiced law. The "third" factor was his advanced study of British and Indian history, and the fourth and the foremost factor was that he was well aware of all the principles of Islam, which bring prosperity in any society. The blend of all above factors made his personality unique so he succeeded in earning the confidence of Muslims. He moved them towards a new direction, which took them towards revivalism of their past glory. His persuasive way of delivering his feelings had vigorous impact on manner of thinking of general Muslim public. They were convinced that their survival is not possible without showing the British that Muslim of India were strong reality, and they could not be ignored so Jinnah's role in budding Muslim Nationalism cannot be ignored. (Rizvi, 2002). He skillfully mobilized common Muslims of India to take part in Pakistan movement and made it a mass-based crusade. (Kiran, 2023)

Now it is also imperative to discuss that almost one hundred year and fifty years ago, that communication was very slow-moving. The only form of media which was available during the 19th century was print media so its role as a "tool" to connect Muslims with their leaders was very crucial and we can say that impressions of great Muslim leaders were only inserted in masses through this medium. Sir Syed Ahmad Khan wrote many books to guide Muslims and to eradicate differences between the rulers and the ruled ones and also founded scientific society in 1863 for the translation of books from English to Urdu and vice versa. He clarified the position of Muslims in front of British by writing a pamphlet *Causes of Indian*

Revolt. This essay was very important primary source to learn not only about the causes of revolt of 1857, but also explained the issues and crisis of Muslims which forced them to raise weapons against British rulers along with Hindus. As this essay was written immediately after war of independence so not only it discussed the initial issues of Muslims but also tried to bridge gap between Muslims and English rulers. Literature like this book helped in reshaping the psyche of Muslims to be together under the umbrella of Muslim nationalism. The circulation of important media newspapers reached from fifty thousand to one lac in the beginning of 20th century. After the Pakistan Resolution, the newspaper in sub-continent were clearly divided into two halves; one advocating Congress and the other supporting the stance of Muslims. Hindu media was dominant due to its majority, but Muslim newspaper boost the morale of Muslims through different articles. While discussing the development of Muslim nationalism in the crucial first half of 20th century in which Muslim nationalism converted into Pakistan movement, the role of print media cannot be overlooked, as it effectively countered Congress and Hindu media propaganda. Zameendar, *Al Hilal*, *Nawa e Waqt*, *Inqilab*, *Eastern Times Dawn*, *Star of India* are some important names in this regard. Dawn Newspaper was established under supervision of Jinnah and played a pivotal role in spreading awareness in Muslim elites.

All the psychological factors discussed above enhanced the growing insecurity among Muslims, who progressively felt distinct from others communities of sub-continent. They realized that they are not only different but also treated unjustly by British rulers and the Hindu majority. This fostered a sense of unity among them and they recognize themselves as a separate nation. It led the way towards Muslim nationalism.

A Cycle of Pride: Way forward to Muslim Nationalism:

Muslims under all these circumstances developed a feeling of humiliation and shame. They were not adapted to this pattern of treatment. They were the ruling entity since centuries, had enjoyed influential positions and were not customary to the discriminatory attitude of the British. The bias and irrational prejudice of British towards Muslims by considering them the sole culprits of the riot against them in 1857 was basically a “social”

shame, in which a specific segment of society is looked down by the superior section i.e. British by considering them inferior. This attitude was really toxic and could be the source of severe depression and discrepancy among Muslim masses as British were degrading Muslims, and instilled demotivation in them and tried to crush them psychologically. (Potter, 2002). All the above factors which influence and affect psychology of Muslims to be together under the phenomenon of Muslim nationalism can also be explained as the cycle of pride. In case, some force tries to bring down the individuals through suppression and degradation, it motivates them to convert their weakness into their motivation and advance their self-confidence. Human mind responses in various ways against unpleasant situations, associated with the self-respect. First is denial of the situation i.e. failure to understand the real situation. The second is “withdrawal” which means running away from the situation instead of facing it. The third mechanism is to start behaving rudely in order to overcome own insecurities and complexes. Another defense mechanism is also a negative tactic i.e. arrogant behavior with others in order to resist their own feeling of worthlessness. If we apply this phenomenon on the situation of Sub-continent after coming under British rule, then we can observe all above attitudes among the locals. Some Muslims, like Abdul Kalam Azad, were not ready to accept that Congress and Hindus were not treating Muslims fairly and honestly. The migration of Muslims towards Afghanistan in Khilafat movement was a kind of escape from the situation which come under the category of withdrawal from the situation. Attitude of Hindus and Sikh towards Muslims after coming under the rule of British falls under the category of rude and arrogant defense mechanism of human mind. (Potter, 2002). There is another type of defense mechanism of human mind against the feeling of shame and humiliation, which is seeking power and took control of the situation. The people who faced disgrace, developed a counter mechanism in their minds to seek power in order to change circumstances and took control of the situation. The strive of Muslims to get independence and efforts to have their separate Islamic state was basically their response against the injustice and oppression of British and Hindus, which was not possible without the strong sense of Muslim nationalism. Once Muslims developed sense of

nationalism in them, it set up sense of pride in them; pride of being Muslims and having their own distinct identity, separate to those of Hindus. This pride had been linked with strength, competence, respect, dignity, integrity and independence in the form of a cycle. All these positive sentiments were developed in Muslims due to the efforts of their great leaders who kept on motivating them to remain hopeful. Allama Iqbal's poetry was the great source of motivation for Muslims in which he tried his best to remind Muslims about their glorious past. Quaid e Azam provoked Muslim youth to work vigorously for their ambition to get back their lost glory. All these psychological sentiments became the base of Muslim Nationalism

Conclusion:

The study has reached to the conclusion that psychological basis of Muslim nationalism was constructed with the social, cultural, religious and historical factors that influenced the lives of Muslims in British-India. These factors influenced the minds of Muslims in such a way that restructured the identity of Muslim community in subcontinent. As discussed in Social Identity theory, Muslims considered themselves separate from other communities in Sub-continent being followers of Islam. Their cultural roots were not weak and they were confidently following all their religious and cultural norms in Mughal era. Muslims felt that they were politically and socially marginalized after British's got control over their country. While developing consciousness that their cultural and religious identity, which had been developed over centuries, was not secure, they became anxious. They were gratified on their core roots and wanted to reduce their vulnerability by all means. British, as a part of their revenge were harsh and biased towards Muslims. Their prejudice towards them in comparison with Hindus was really insensitive and insolent. Just connecting it to Relative deprivation theory of psychology; grievances, insecurities and penury faced by Muslims because of economic injustice, initially developed sense of indignance, but then eagerly enhanced their morale to strive for their unity. They used that feeling of disgrace as the signal of hope, so the degradation of the whole Muslim community by British became a useful helper for them to fortify themselves as Muslim nationalists, rather than making it a destructive force in their social life. The conversion of negative impacts of

rude attitude of British and Hindus into a positive force of Muslim Nationalism was the turning point for Muslims, which changed their destiny. Sir Syed Ahmad Khan started to console Muslims and tried to drag them towards some harmless changes in their mode of living and style of thinking. He encouraged Muslims to get familiar with English language, so that they could connect with British and be able to present their concerns and put their demands in front of them. This was the need of that hour. It also justified the acculturation theory of sociology which explains that people with different cultures when have to encounter regularly, they gradually face a cultural change in their lifestyles and also in society as a whole. Also Muslims turned to be little more curious about the perseverance of their individuality, which circuitously promote Muslim Nationalism. The understanding of the psychological base of Muslim Nationalism in sub-continent is important today because in this globalized world, some states like Pakistan are multi cultured and multi ethnic. There may be gradually developing frustrations and issues among minorities due to some unjust and biased policies, so the policy makers while formulating the internal policies, must keep in view the above psychological factors affecting different factions of society in a negative way, which may cause instability and anarchy in their state.

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